

CURRENT STATUS OF THE USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN BUSINESS EMAIL

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Annotation: *Every state also the number of the digital economy in uzbekistan formation and development of information and communication technologies (ICT) with the development of intertwined. A wide range of studies have been conducted on the analysis of the digital economy, the economy, public administration and various sectors of society to penetrate its specific feature is the fact that comprehensive ict.*

Keywords: *email, digital logistics, API, e-commerce, digital ecosystem.*

According to the survey results, experts mam certainlakatda the digital economyin the successful development of the role of the state stressed the importance of coordination in the introduction he came to the conclusion that performs the function of advanced technologies. Today the president and the government of the republic of uzbekistan the development of ict and its all spheres of life of society, paying particular attention to the introduction of mass. The legislative chamber and the senate in reference to the president of the republic of uzbekistan Sh.M.To assign the year 2020 "science-the year of education and the development of the digital economy," declared made a radical turn in the development of the digital economy in the country this year that should be noted. "First of all, construction, energy, agriculture and water resources, transportation, geology, cartography, health, education and the field of digitization, it is necessary to the full archives. These quests are given within two months of the "digital economy – 2030" we have completed to develop a program". On 5 October the president of the country in the year 2020 Sh.M.Assign R in the republic of economy aqamli directed to the accelerated development UP-6079 digital "digital Uzbekistan – 2030" strategy for the effective implementation and adoption of measures"on¹ the decree was signed.

Also it must be said that the introduction of ict change the role of active information (transformasiya), particularly an increase in network

activity to other sectors of mutual dependence, the role of science in structural imbalances in the labor market and the economy to the service sector leads to increase in the share of yamm. Also, this period of development on the one hand, the condition of the maximum period of uncertainty for the future, while on the second hand is xarakterliki high dynamics of development. The second stage of formation to be a characteristic feature of the old structures (institutions, relationships, agents) and at the same time the formation of new trends to update or completely lose it.

The formation of the digital economy in the republic of the production of products and services which are associated with intellectual abilities and the role of relevant types of economic activity is determined by the structural changes in the economy have increased. Growth parameters directly to its defined theoretical knowledge in the development of the digital economy, innovation and human capital formation of a ground creates. Digital economy in uzbekistan is the basis of the material in relation to the production of a significantly larger contribution of human capital in terms of the value of the service sector is complex, with the description of. Today, some formed and in the other network activity related to the collected data is increasing. Also, the word on the basis of the large volume of information from and about the increase of the share of service has been intensively used, these are: education, development and innovasiyalar development, and intellectual information and communication services you can add.

Email systemic reforms in the field of communication, the universal postal union of the republic of uzbekistan to ensure the fulfillment of the obligation which arises from unconditional act and by the ministry of development of information technology and kommunikasiyalari "uzbekistan pochta si" joint-stock company is being undertaken by noteworthy. Today, a strong competitive environment in the market of e-mail communication came into being. 575 units kur'erlik mail services major companies and local private companies and at international level by showing it. According to statistics, by the year 2019 260,0 billion soums kur'erlik mail and the enterprise services provided.

"Uzbekistan pochta si" joint-stock company cover all regions of the country in the system, more than 2 thousand units of 7 thousand employees maintain them functioning, but over the years, attention to the area, which is not provided because of the role of the postal

service is going to decrease, in particular, was the closing of post offices in the last fifteen years 1 300 thousand. Last year, only 10 percent coming from overseas who send 6 thousand tons, 30 percent of services kur'erlik had to contribute to the national post, that's all.

LITERATURE LIST:

1.The decision of the president of the republic of uzbekistan"Open the digital ecosystem" on the organization of 17.11.2021 –PP-14

2.October 5, signed by the president of the country in the year 2020 UP-6079 digital "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030" strategy for the effective implementation and adoption of measures" the decree <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/5031048>

3. Tsifrovoy transport i logistika-Simeon.A.K .11.02.2019

4. Preimutshestva tsifrovoy ekonomika – Mustafakulov.U.U.09.02.2020

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